

1 **HLA-V is a marker of transformation in human cells.**

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6 We report here the discovery of a class I HLA receptor, HLA-V, expressed selectively by transformed cells.
7 HLA-V was a likely cognate receptor for the natural killer cell receptor *KIR2DL3*. Expression of HLA-V was
8 selectively enriched in Kir2DL3+ cells. Specificity of HLA-V for transformed status was supported by
9 observation of HLA-V induction by p53 point mutants and by loss of HLA-V expression following silencing
10 of an oncogenic homeobox factor in a manner that was quantitatively proportionate with reduction in
11 ECT2. *KIR2DL3* expression was specifically associated with rearrangement of the gamma delta TCR,
12 indicating the existence of a clearance mechanism by which HLA-V expression on transformed cells was
13 targeted by *KIR2DL3*+ NK cells which in turn recruited gamma delta T-cells for elimination of transformed
14 cells (tumor surveillance).
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